

SUICIDAL IDEATION AMONG THE COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study is to find out the factor that causes suicidal ideation among the college students 307 students studying in the nine colleges of education in Villupuram district of Tamil Nadu were selected using purposive random sampling. Suicidal Ideation Scale developed and standardized by Visvanathan and Mariyammal (2017) was used to collect data and the collected data were statistically analysed using SPSS. The study reveals that the level only 0.98% of the college students have high level of suicidal ideation. No significant difference was found between the male and female college students, the urban and rural college students, the government and private college students, and the college students of nuclear and joint family in their suicidal ideation factors. Significant difference was found among the birth order and parents' occupation of college students in their suicidal ideation factors. Further the study reveals that the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation is either study reasons or psychological reasons among the college students.

Key Words: Suicidal Ideation & College Students

Introduction:

Human life is precious and there is nothing in the world that can ever stand in par with life. It is God/nature given and none has the right to take it away. Death is a misery and the impact of death is enormous and inexplicable. It affects many even after their death. It is a great loss for parents, spouse, children, relatives, friends, well-wishers and all. While death is pre-determined and inevitable, it cannot be taken either by self or others. Of all forms of death, suicide is horrible, unacceptable and a crime. Yet, at times, some commit suicide and some others attempt suicide. Suicidal ideation means wanting to take your own life or thinking about suicide (Purse, 2018). It is common to see people with suicidal ideation seek help or leave suicide notes on social media before attempting suicide (Aladağ, et al. 2018) and it is really pathetic. The causes for suicide may be varying and yet it could be prevented if identified at the right time and timely help/guidance is given.

Review of Literature:

Arria, O'Grady, Caldeira, Vincent, Wilcox, and Wish (2009) investigated suicide ideation among college students and found that an estimated 6% wt of first-year students at this university had current suicide ideation. Depressive symptoms, low social support, affective dysregulation, and father-child conflict were each independently associated with suicide ideation. Jo, Ju An, and Sohn (2011) conducted a qualitative content analysis of suicidal ideation in Korean college students and found out that Buddhism and Confucianism had influence on reasons to not attempting suicide behavior as the inhibitor of suicidal ideation. Silvia, Santos, Soares, and Pardno (2014) examined Suicidal ideation and associated factors among adolescents in northeastern Brazil and concluded that suicidal ideation was associated with female sex, involvement in fights, and illicit drug use. Patricia, Casey, Dunn, Kelly, and Birkbeck (2018) investigated the factors associated with suicidal ideation in the general population and found out that age, marriage, concern by others and severity of depressed mood independently increased or decreased the odds of suicidal ideation overall. Further an interaction between life events and social supports was identified.

Significance of the Study:

As you think, you are and you will be. Thoughts become our actions. The thought of committing suicide formation emerges inside and it intensifies due to continuous thinking on the same thought. The idea formation on committing suicide in an individual is known as suicidal ideation. Experience of negative and failures, unable to achieve the goals, personal dissatisfaction, financial problems, emotional issues, depression, academic failure, social discrimination, loneliness, and the feeling of being abandoned by all in the world are some of the causes of committing suicide. Evidence suggests that, for many young people, a breakdown in personal relationships or experiencing a personal crisis can immediately precede an attempt to end life (Rivers, 201), All these varying causes may be classified under psychological reasons, academic reasons, health reasons, social and economic reasons. It is unfortunate that the rate of suicide is increasing day by day even among the youth and it suggests that the presence of suicidal ideation among the youth. School students and college students also commit suicide, sometimes. Reports from the World Health Organization (WHO) indicate that suicide accounts for the largest share of the intentional injury burden in developed countries (Nock, et al., 2008). This study aims at finding out the prevalence of suicidal ideation among the college students. The sample for the study is taken from the colleges of education and the findings of the study will be of immense value in saving the lives of the students by offering proper guidance and help. Hence this study is undertaken to find out the factor that influence the suicidal ideation among the college students with a sense of social responsibility and commitment.

Since, very few studies have been taken on the suicidal ideation among the college students, the findings will be very significant, innovative and informative.

Operational Definition of the Terms:

Suicidal Ideation:

It refers to unusual preoccupation with suicidal thoughts in mind of the individuals.

Suicidal Ideation Scale:

It is a tool to measure the level of suicidal thoughts in mind of the individuals. In this study it refers to the 4 point scale prepared by the investigators.

Higher Secondary Students:

It refers to students studying in the 11th and 12th standards in the Higher Secondary Course as per the pattern of the Government of Tamil Nadu.

Objectives:

- To find out the level of suicidal ideation among the college students.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in suicidal ideation of college students with regard to gender, locality, type of management, type of family, birth order and parents' occupation.

Hypotheses:

- H₀1: There is no significant difference between the male and female college students in their suicidal ideation.
 H₀2: There is no significant difference between the urban and rural college students in their suicidal ideation.
 H₀3: There is no significant difference between the government and private college students in their suicidal ideation.
 H₀4: There is no significant difference between the college students of nuclear and joint family in their suicidal ideation factors.
 H₀5: There is no significant difference among the birth order of college students in their suicidal ideation factors.
 H₀6: There is no significant difference among the college students in their suicidal ideation factors with regard to their parents' occupation.

Methodology:

Survey method was adapted for this study. Purposive random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample of 307 students studying nine colleges of education as the sample from Villupuram district of Tamil Nadu. 'Suicidal Ideation Scale' constructed and validated by the author and Mariyammal(2017) was used for collecting the data. It is a four point scale with 64 total items in the form of statement. It assesses the suicidal ideation considering five factors: Psychological, study, health, social and economic factor. All the items were positive in nature and they were assigned the value of 0, 1, 2, and 3. Split half technique (odd/even scores) was used to find out the reliability of the tool and it was found to be 0.82. The collected data were statistically analyzed using 't' test, and ANOVA.

Results:

Objective Testing: To find out the level of suicidal ideation among the college students.

Table 1: Level of suicidal ideation among the college students

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Suicidal Ideation	103	33.55	201	65.47	3	0.98

It is inferred from Table 1 that 33.55% of college students have low level of suicidal ideation, 65.47% of them have moderate, and 0.98% of them have high level of suicidal ideation.

Figure 1: Level of suicidal ideation among the college students

Hypotheses Testing:

H₀1: There is no significant difference between the male and female college students in their suicidal ideation factors.

Table 2: Difference between the Male and Female College Students in their Suicidal Ideation

Suicidal Ideation Factors	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' Value	p Value	S/NS
1. Psychological Factor	Male	66	17.59	5.093	1.58	.113	NS
	Female	241	18.79	5.541			
2. Study Factor	Male	66	34.53	15.479	0.08	.930	NS
	Female	241	34.36	13.427			
3. Health Factor	Male	66	6.26	3.639	0.23	.818	NS
	Female	241	6.36	3.106			
4. Social Factor	Male	66	8.68	6.817	0.99	.319	NS
	Female	241	7.78	6.457			
5. Economic Factor	Male	66	8.11	5.663	2.79	.005*	S
	Female	241	6.38	4.039			
Overall	Male	66	75.17	21.814	0.57	.563	NS
	Female	241	73.67	17.625			

Note: The table value of 't' at 5% level is 1.96; Greater than 1.96 is significant (S); Less than 1.96 is not significant (NS). The table value of P is 0.05; 0.05 and less than 0.05 is significant (S); Greater than 0.05 is not significant (NS).

Figure 2: Difference between the Male and Female College Students in their Suicidal Ideation Factors

It is inferred from Table 2 that there is no significant difference between the male and female college students in their suicidal ideation factors in total and in all the factors except economic factor. When comparing the mean scores of all the five suicidal ideation factors, the mean score of the study factor (34.53, 34.36) is the highest and it reveals that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts. Next to the study factor is the psychological factor with the mean scores (17.59, 18.79) revealing that that the psychological factor is the next predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts among the college students with regard to gender.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between the urban and rural college students in their suicidal ideation factors.

Table 3: Difference between the Urban and Rural College Students in their Suicidal Ideation

Suicidal Ideation Factors	Locality	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' Value	p Value	S/NS
1. Psychological Factor	Urban	93	18.82	5.718	0.59	.550	NS
	Rural	214	18.41	5.356			
2. Study Factor	Urban	93	34.75	13.807	0.29	.768	NS
	Rural	214	34.24	13.923			
3. Health Factor	Urban	93	6.69	3.135	1.25	.211	NS
	Rural	214	6.19	3.255			
4. Social Factor	Urban	93	7.88	6.961	0.15	.875	NS
	Rural	214	8.01	6.358			
5. Economic Factor	Urban	93	7.02	4.496	0.69	.489	NS
	Rural	214	6.64	4.484			
Overall	Urban	93	75.16	18.890	0.72	.469	NS
	Rural	214	73.49	18.461			

Note: The table value of 't' at 5% level is 1.96; Greater than 1.96 is significant (S); Less than 1.96 is not significant (NS). The table value of P is 0.05; 0.05 and less than 0.05 is significant (S); Greater than 0.05 is not significant (NS).

Figure 3: Difference between the Urban and Rural College Students in their Suicidal Ideation Factors

It is inferred from Table 3 that there is no significant difference between the urban and rural college students in their suicidal ideation factors in total and in all the factors. When comparing the mean scores of all the five suicidal ideation factors, the mean scores of the study factor (34.75, 34.24) is the highest and it reveals that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts. Next to the study factor is the psychological factor with the mean scores (18.82, 18.41) revealing that that the psychological factor is the next predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts among the college students with regard to locality. H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the government and private college students in their suicidal ideation factors.

Table 4: Difference between the Government and Private College Students in their Suicidal Ideation Factors

Suicidal Ideation Factors	Type of College	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' Value	p Value	S/ NS
1. Psychological Factor	Government	106	19.34	5.241	1.88	.060	NS
	Private	201	18.11	5.541			
2. Study Factor	Government	106	32.42	12.842	1.81	.070	NS
	Private	201	35.44	14.300			
3. Health Factor	Government	106	5.34	2.885	4.04	.000	S
	Private	201	6.87	3.272			
4. Social Factor	Government	106	7.95	6.541	0.03	.972	NS
	Private	201	7.98	6.548			
5. Economic Factor	Government	106	7.14	4.072	1.10	.270	NS
	Private	201	6.55	4.684			
Overall	Government	106	72.20	17.433	1.23	0.21	NS
	Private	201	74.94	19.127			

Note: The table value of 't' at 5% level is 1.96; Greater than 1.96 is significant (S); Less than 1.96 is not significant (NS). The table value of P is 0.05; 0.05 and less than 0.05 is significant(S); Greater than 0.05 is not significant (NS).

Figure 4: Difference between the Govt. and Private College Students in their Suicidal Ideation Factors

It is inferred from Table 4 that there is no significant difference between the government and private college students in their suicidal ideation factors in total and in all the factors except health factor. When

comparing the mean scores of all the five suicidal ideation factors, the mean scores of the study factor (32.42, 35.44) is the highest and it reveals that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts. Next to the study factor is the psychological factor with the mean scores (19.34, 18.11) revealing that that the psychological factor is the next predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts among the college students with regard to type of college.

H₀4: There is no significant difference between the college students of nuclear and joint family in their suicidal ideation factors.

Table 5: Difference between the college students of nuclear and joint family in their Suicidal Ideation Factors

Suicidal Ideation Factors	Type of family	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' Value	p Value	S/ NS
1. Psychological Factor	Nuclear	163	18.59	5.312	0.18	.852	NS
	Joint	144	18.47	5.644			
2. Study Factor	Nuclear	163	34.13	13.669	0.36	.719	NS
	Joint	144	34.70	14.129			
3. Health Factor	Nuclear	163	6.41	3.191	0.41	.677	NS
	Joint	144	6.26	3.266			
4. Social Factor	Nuclear	163	8.30	6.646	0.94	.347	NS
	Joint	144	7.60	6.409			
5. Economic Factor	Nuclear	163	6.72	4.652	0.11	.906	NS
	Joint	144	6.78	4.302			
Overall	Nuclear	163	74.15	18.769	0.160	.873	NS
	Joint	144	73.81	18.421			

Note: The table value of 't' at 5% level is 1.96; Greater than 1.96 is significant (S); Less than 1.96 is not significant (NS). The table value of P is 0.05; 0.05 and less than 0.05 is significant(S); Greater than 0.05 is not significant (NS).

Figure 5: Difference between the college students of nuclear and joint family in their Suicidal Ideation Factors

It is inferred from Table 5 that there is no significant difference between the college students of nuclear and joint family in their suicidal ideation factors in total and in all the factors. When comparing the mean scores of all the five suicidal ideation factors, the mean scores of the study factor (34.13, 34.70) is the highest and it reveals that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts. Next to the study factor is the psychological factor with the mean scores (18.59, 18.47) revealing that that the psychological factor is the next predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts among the college students with regard to type of family.

H₀5: There is no significant difference among the birth order of college students in their suicidal ideation factors.

Table 6: Difference among the Birth Order of College Students in their suicidal Ideation Factors

Suicidal Ideation Factors	Birth Order	N	Mean	Source of Variance	Mean Square	F	p value	S/ NS
1. Psychological Factor	1 st born	133	19.20	Between Groups	56.809	1.916	.149	NS
	2 nd born	96	17.80					
	3 rd & above	78	18.31	Within Groups	29.654			
2. Study Factor	1 st born	133	36.52	Between Groups	1881.575	5.021	.007	S

3.	Health Factor	2 nd born	96	30.81	Within Groups	56959.943	.916	.401	NS
		3 rd & above	78	35.19					
		1 st born	133	6.56	Between Groups	9.511			
4.	Social Factor	2 nd born	96	6.36	Within Groups	10.387	3.550	.030	S
		3 rd & above	78	5.94					
		1 st born	133	8.20	Between Groups	149.130			
5.	Economic Factor	2 nd born	96	6.70	Within Groups	19.804	3.349	.036	S
		3 rd & above	78	5.74					
		1 st born	133	7.38	Between Groups	66.315			
Overall		2 nd born	96	70.63	Within Groups	335.737	5.272	.006	S
		3 rd & above	78	71.55					
		1 st born	133	77.86	Between Groups	1769.953			

Note: At 5% level of significance, for (2,304) df the table value of 'F' is 3.02; Greater than 3.02 is significant (S); Less than 3.02 is not significant (NS).

Figure 6: Difference among the Birth Order of College Students in their suicidal Ideation Factors

It is inferred from Table 6 that there is significant difference among the birth order of college students in their suicidal ideation factors in total and in all the factors, except psychological and health factors. When comparing the mean scores of all the five suicidal ideation factors, the mean scores of the study factor (36.53, 30.81, 35.19) is the highest and it reveals that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts. Next to the study factor is the psychological factor with the mean scores (19.20, 17.80, 18.31) revealing that that the psychological factor is the next predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts among the college students with regard to birth order.

H₀6: There is no significant difference among the college students in their suicidal ideation factors with regard to their parents' occupation.

Table 7: Difference among the College Students in their suicidal Ideation Factors with regard to their Parents' Occupation

Suicidal Ideation Factors	Parents' Occupation	N	Mean	Source of Variance	Mean Square	F	p value	S/ NS
1. Psychological Factor	Both working	98	18.06	Between Groups	62.602	2.114	.123	NS
	Father only	152	19.16	Within Groups	29.616			
	Mother only	57	17.67					
2. Study Factor	Both working	98	35.17	Between Groups	631.957	3.337	.037	S
	Father only	152	35.49	Within Groups	189.400			
	Mother only	57	30.16					
3. Health Factor	Both working	98	34.40	Between Groups	7.312	.703	.496	NS
	Father only	152	6.65	Within Groups	10.402			
	Mother only	57	6.16					

4. Social Factor	Both working	98	9.36	Between Groups	139.630	3.319	.038	S
	Father only	152	7.39	Within Groups	42.071			
	Mother only	57	7.14					
5. Economic Factor	Both working	98	7.28	Between Groups	40.058	2.005	.136	NS
	Father only	152	6.24	Within Groups	19.977			
	Mother only	57	7.23					
Overall	Both working	98	76.52	Between Groups	1201.960	3.541	.030	S
	Father only	152	74.44	Within Groups	339.474			
	Mother only	57	68.46					

Note: At 5% level of significance, for (2,304) df the table value of 'F' is 3.02; Greater than 3.02 is significant (S); Less than 3.02 is not significant (NS).

Figure 7: Difference among the College Students in their suicidal Ideation Factors with regard to their Parents' Occupation

It is inferred from Table 7 that there is significant difference among the college students in their suicidal ideation factors with regard to their parents' occupation. In total and in all the factors, except study and social factors. When comparing the mean scores of all the five suicidal ideation factors, the mean scores of the study factor (35.17, 35.49, 30.16) is the highest and it reveals that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts. Next to the study factor is the psychological factor with the mean scores (18.06, 19.16, 17.67) revealing that that the psychological factor is the next predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts among the college students with regard to parents' occupation.

Major Findings:

- No significant difference was found between the male and female college students in their suicidal ideation factors. Further, it was found out that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation, followed by the psychological factor among the college students with regard to gender.
- No significant difference between the urban and rural college students in their suicidal ideation factors. Further, it was found out that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation, followed by the psychological factor among the college students with regard to locality.
- No significant difference was found between the government and private college students in their suicidal ideation factors. Further, it was found out that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation, followed by the psychological factor among the college students with regard to type of college.
- No significant difference was found between the college students of nuclear and joint family in their suicidal ideation factors. Further, it is found out that study factor is the predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation, followed by the psychological factor among the college students with regard to type of family.
- Significant difference was found among the birth order of college students in their suicidal ideation factors. Further it was found out that study factor is predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts, followed by the psychological factor with regard to birth order.

- Significant difference was found among the college students in their suicidal ideation factors with regard to their parents' occupation. Further it was found out that study factor is predominant factor that leads to suicidal ideation/thoughts, followed by the psychological factor with regard to parents' occupation.

Conclusion

It is concluded that not even one percent of the college students have high level of suicidal ideation and this is very positive and encouraging. Yet majority of them have moderate and some have low level of suicidal ideation and it suggests that appropriate remedial and guidance should be given to help them come out from this thought. The predominant factor for the cause of suicidal ideation is study reason and psychological reason and hence these issues need to be addressed wisely at the appropriate level with the support of parents, teachers, friends and counselors throwing a new light in the field of educational research.

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